

Knowledge Representation for Algorithmic Auditing

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Abstract: Knowledge is central to cognition, and adequate knowledge representation is necessary to ensure the correct functioning of intelligent systems at all levels. Knowledge Auditing methodologies in use however do not typically address the requirements for evaluating the consistency of logical and functional knowledge representation constructs that support the correct execution of system processes. This paper relates knowledge representation as a contributing factor to bias in AI, and puts forward knowledge representation quality and adequacy criteria that can be incorporated in any data, knowledge and algorithmic auditing methodology in use. .

Keywords: Keyword, keyword..

1 Introduction and Motivation

Despite the proliferation of Knowledge Based technologies and Knowledge Representation (KR) methods and techniques in AI since the beginning of the computing age, their impact on system fairness and bias and their role to ensure the logical and functional consistency and integrity of systems has not been explicitly addressed. This paper investigates the relation between KR (Knowledge Representation), fairness and bias. It provides a definition for systemic bias and an overview of auditing methodologies including algorithmic audits.

A set of criteria and a checklist for the evaluation of KR quality and adequacy is provided as a guideline to complement algorithmic audits. As an example, a module KR is added to the KAF methodological framework which is also briefly summarized.

2 Semantics and Knowledge Representation

In recent years research in semantic technology has been influenced by the development of semantic web standards such as OWL and RDF, however the relationship between semantics and knowledge representation at large is historical and long standing both in classical sciences such as mathematics as well as in linguistics, and other spheres of human thinking, predating the semantic web and related published standards by several decades [1]. Semantics in its original interpretation relates to the ability of words to capture and convey meaning thanks to the relations between them. This can be done using more than one modelling approach, for example also using markup languages such as SysML [2]. “Systems semantics extends the denotational semantics of programming languages to a semantics for the description of arbitrary systems, including objects that are not computations in any sense. By defining different meaning functions, the same formal description may be used to denote different system properties, such as structure, behavior, component cost, and performance aspects ” [3]

KR, especially symbolic KR, which relies on natural language representations as a mechanism to capture the relationship between words and concepts, is intended to capture and to some extent formalize and make explicit the semantics of natural languages. In this paper semantics is considered inherent to all Knowledge Representation methods and techniques and not related to any specific implementation language or standard. Ultimately any valid first order logic construct can be mapped to OWL and RDF semantics.

3. Accountability And Algorithmic Bias

Intelligent systems powered by algorithms have become pervasive and embedded, and algorithmic accountability is an imperative quality criterion for AI, whereby plausible justifications is necessary for reliable automated system’s outputs. Many types of bias are identified and discussed in a growing body of Machine Learning literature [5] and are being addressed in academic research as well in the praxis with initiatives that aim to

disseminate principles and good practices summarised as FAT (Fair Accountable and Transparent)¹. These include:

- Responsibility: Externally visible avenues of redress for adverse individual or societal effects, and designate an internal role for the person who is responsible for the timely remedy of such issues.
- Explainability: Ensure that algorithmic decisions as well as any data driving those decisions can be explained to end-users and other stakeholders in non-technical terms.
- Accuracy: Identify, log, and articulate sources of error and uncertainty so that expected and worst case implications can be understood and inform mitigation procedures.
 - Auditability: Enable interested third parties to probe, understand, and review the behavior of the algorithm through disclosure of information that enables monitoring, checking, or criticism, including through provision of detailed documentation, technically suitable APIs, and permissive terms of use.
- Fairness: Ensure that algorithmic decisions do not create discriminatory or unjust impacts when comparing across different demographics (e.g. race, sex, etc).

Attempts are underway to devise a hierarchical conceptual structure such as a taxonomy for Bias, however this is proving challenging. The list of biases is long, innumerable distortions and flaws characterize human thinking and consequently machines designed by humans. Biases can be grouped according to different needs and views and the choice of taxonomic arrangement is determined by the worldview. the task, the norms in the field of practice or discipline in which it is applied. When taking a systemic, high level view however, most types of biases can be arranged in a handful of clusters which are entangled and co-dependent, generating a type of bias which is defined here as ‘systemic’. Systemic bias therefore can be defined as any bias that impacts the fairness and the accuracy of a system’s outcome and that cannot be ascribed to a single factor, because its underlying causes are co-dependent.

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<https://www.fatml.org/resources/principles-for-accountable-algorithms>

3.1 Disentangling Systemic Bias

There exist different ways to categorize bias, depending on epistemological perspectives, constraints and other factors. Some types of bias are well understood and exist aside from AI implementation such as cognitive bias, research bias, etc. A single taxonomy of biases can be problematic and resource intensive to formulate, at the time of writing there have been no definitive results in this direction. However some broad categories can be generalized from literature and organised from the most basic level (perceptual) to the most generalized level (systemic) as follows:

Perceptual Perceptual biases are errors that disrupt and distort the perceptual process, thus leading to faulty judgements. These can occur because we, as humans, attempt to create shortcuts of understanding

Cognitive Tversky and Kahneman introduced the term ‘cognitive bias’ to describe people’s systematic but purportedly flawed patterns of responses to judgment and decision problems. There are many kinds of cognitive biases [5]

Representational A representational bias defines the states in a search space. Typically, this search space is the space of hypotheses, a strong representational bias for the hypothesis space implies a small hypothesis space; a weak representational bias implies a large hypothesis space.[6] In addition, Representation Bias can be characterised further as a type of knowledge misrepresentation. Ie, if some fact is false, partially true, incomplete or placed out of context, this can give rise to misrepresentation, ie, the representation does not correspond to truth, it is also called a representation bias.

Epistemological Relating to demarcation, confirmation, and scientific method and experiment.

Ontological Philosophical bias relating to *basic implicit assumptions* what exist (ontology)

Procedural Procedural bias is where an unfair amount of pressure is applied to the subjects, forcing them to complete their responses quickly. For example, employees asked to fill out a questionnaire during their break period are likely to rush, rather than reading the questions properly.

Systemic: Any bias that cannot be ascribed to a single cause and is generated by a combination of the other types of bias. Real world problem spaces such as systemic deviation are complex and the product of emergence and of the entanglement of different factors. Solutions cannot be found following a single path, biased outcomes cannot be attributed to a single variable in an algorithm. Similarly, when designing, implementing and deploying AI systems, due to the complexity of the interactions between controlled computational environments and real life deployments, it can be difficult to pinpoint system malfunction to a single factor resulting in systemic functional risks and functionally or ethically 'wrong' outcomes. Systemic bias is therefore defined as emergent from the combination of one or more or all of these types of high level bias groupings

Image: Systemic Bias

3.2 Knowledge Representation

Knowledge representation (KR) in particular Symbolic KR consists of techniques and methods devised to capture system logic so that it can be leveraged by algorithms. KR can also be useful in mitigating at least in part the lack of transparency of machine learning and algorithmic opacity, a role which is not fully explored. In addition to the well documented canonical roles of KR in supporting the development of AI and well documented in a long list of textbooks[7], the term KR is generalized to indicate:

- A multifaceted discipline
- A field of study in Computer Science, jurisprudence, learning and other fields KR as a technique/process
- A set of activities in Knowledge Modeling and Knowledge Engineering applied to systems development KR as artifacts
- Knowledge encoded and implemented as a product of KR activities (for example a graph, an ontology or an algorithm)

3.3. Deepfakes As Knowledge Misrepresentation

The social, technical and economic impact of bias, especially in the case of systemic, entangled biases cannot be estimated, and debiasing can add considerable costs in terms of time and money to the software and systems development. In AI, and specifically AI powered by Machine Learning, bias can generally be directly or indirectly mapped to knowledge misrepresentation. This is demonstrated by the case of Deepfakes [8] where hidden algorithmic manipulations deliberately distort knowledge representation and produce a false output intended to manipulate public opinion, create misinformation and confusion which costs time and money to rectify. Technically speaking, an algorithm can function correctly and no error of flaw is apparent without considerable expert human discernment and skill to investigate what type of hidden automated permutations deliver the capability of fictional outputs. Knowledge misrepresentation, in different forms can cause 'Systemic Deviation' a behavioral and functional shift of a system from its intended purpose.

For example, systemic deviation can occur when:

- a) A system is designed with the intent to disguise its real aim to achieve a different goal from what it appears to be designed for. For example in the case of software or hardware designed to spy but marketed as technology to protect privacy is considered systemic deviation
- b) When a system is deliberately designed to function in a different way from what is stated. The system says it offers localization, but it is used for tracking and passes the tracking data to unauthorized third parties.
- c) A system designed to function in a certain way for a certain (ethical) purpose, is misused and made to function to fulfill the exact opposite (unethical) purpose as in the case of health monitoring software designed to save patient lives, which can be used by medics to make end of life decisions based on sociological or economic factors (such as not providing Covid treatment to a tetraplegic patient on some statistical rationale).²
- c) A system knowledge representation is deliberately manipulated to produce an output that does not conform correctly to the intended KR model

4. Auditing: Data, Knowledge, Algorithms

There are many kinds of system compliance auditing processes and methods used in technology engineering and management to ensure that systems do what they say they do. Audits are defined as “independent evaluations of conformance of software products and processes to applicable regulations, standards, guidelines, plans, specifications, and procedures” [9]. In organisational settings they are defined as tools for interrogating complex processes, often to determine whether they comply with company policy, industry standards or regulations [10].

4.1. Data Auditing

In software engineering, data dictionaries and data catalogues contain data

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<https://www.washingtonpost.com/health/2020/07/05/coronavirus-disability-death/>

sets and their properties and attributes maintained by developers for the purpose of system design [11]. From an organisational point of view, data audits are catalogues of datasets compiled and published by institutions and comprising digital assets, such as learning objects, electronic journal articles, publications, web resources and datasets. One example of published methodology for Data Audits is DAF which was scoped to handle mostly research data assets and constitutes the methodological basis for knowledge auditing methodologies which evolved from it [19].

4.2 Knowledge Auditing

A Knowledge Audit consists typically of an inventory, a knowledge map and a knowledge flow. Knowledge Auditing (KA) is an established practice in Knowledge Management, sometimes referred to as knowledge inventory and knowledge assessment. Its purpose is to provide an inventory of assets and core information about them, as well to identify knowledge gaps [12]

KA typically answer the questions such as

what knowledge exists? And what knowledge is missing? [13]

Additional KA techniques include Knowledge surveys, Assets mapping, Intellectual Capital (IC) Inventorying, Knowledge Landscape Mapping, Competitive Knowledge Analysis, Knowledge Flowcharting and Analysis (KFA) and others [14]. Knowledge Audits are typically carried out on site whereby auditors visit the premises of a company or organisation owning the Knowledge Assets, often for the purpose of valuation on behalf of a buyer in relation to a takeover and are carried out behind closed doors, their outcomes are not public. Knowledge Auditing however has been used also as a baseline method to audit Open Data, Open Knowledge and Open Access resources, produced by the increasingly widely accepted policies which mandate the accessible and transparent access of resources produced by publicly funded research. In public sector affairs, KA can be used to provide a measure of the extent to which a public administration publishes knowledge and to what extent is this knowledge accessible, answering the question:

What knowledge generated by public funding can be openly (without payment or subscription required) accessed online?

4.2.1 The Knowledge Audit Framework

Initially devised to fulfil the requirements doctoral research project (DMEM University of Strathclyde, 2009-2012) [15], KAF is a technical instrument modelled on DAF (Data Audit Framework) developed a few years earlier by Glasgow University for the purpose of data curation and preservation. The initial purpose of KAF was to enable the systematic evaluation of Knowledge Sharing Artefacts and Practices adoption, with particular emphasis on reuse, vs the focus on data inventorying of the earlier DAF. The need for remote auditing arose because the doctoral research project, funded by EPSRC, required access to knowledge (documents, drawings publications) developed a consortium of research partners, mostly UK universities in collaborations with companies in the defense sector. To obtain access to premises where the repositories of knowledge were people, projects and documents to be audited it was necessary to obtain security clearance, however the criteria for granting or dyeing such security clearance to access premises were not disclosed, and were seemingly inscrutable and arbitrary policies. Although publicly funded Universities and Research Funding Councils declare open access mandates, due to complex contractual arrangements, private companies involved in the research consortia could grant or refuse access to their premises and their knowledge repositories without having to provide reasons or explanations for their decisions. KAF was devised as an instrument to carry out, at least in part, remote knowledge audits of research outcomes - ie, knowledge generated by research - of publicly funded projects in the systems engineering research domain and make them auditable. The primary goal of KAF therefore is to enable an objective evaluation of what knowledge resources are publicly shared, their ease of accessibility via open web searchers and where they are located and who is (or is not) responsible for them. The main strengths of KAF are that a) supports remote audits carried out via online searches b) the results of the audits are replicable - given the same search criteria two different auditors would come up with very similar results.

KAF serves as the model for an algorithmic auditing methodology that integrates KR criteria.

4. 2.2 Algorithm Auditing

Algorithmic auditing has entered the software development practice and is used generally as a posteriori, i.e. after the algorithm has been compiled, to evaluate its fairness and identify possible biases. Innumerable examples of algorithmic bias are provided in literature and frameworks attempting to mitigate such biases however address the artifact level (the knowledge artefacts) rather than the reasoning and inferences contained in the algorithm [16].

TYPE OF Algorithmic Auditing	STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
Code Audits	Straightforward	Code not shared
Non Invasive User Audits	Ease of use	Sampling limited
Scraping Audits	Easily automated	Breach of terms of uses and CFAA regulations
Sock puppet	Provides anonymity	Fake users/fabrication/reliability
Crowdsourced/ collaborative	High volume	High cost/requires organisational effort

Table 1 Source: 18

Algorithmic auditing methods evaluated empirically but they have not been systematically benchmarked at the time of writing. Examples with different emphases, weaknesses and strengths are summarized in Table 1 [18] None of the algorithmic auditing methods surveyed tackles the bias deriving from Knowledge Misrepresentation and the lack of Knowledge Representation adequacy.

5. Knowledge Representation For Algorithmic Audits

In relation to Knowledge Representation, a Knowledge Audit seeks to answer questions such as:

Is knowledge adequately represented to fulfil fairness requirements within the scope and goals of the system?

5.1 Criteria for Auditing KR

The body of knowledge of KR in AI is vast, providing innumerable computational techniques and methods for the modelling of Knowledge in intelligent systems, yet the fundamental purpose of KR can easily become lost: to represent knowledge adequately. Understanding and addressing the different types of adequacy in AI is not trivial. The first and foremost risk of any representational device is to either not represent knowledge (omission) or to mis-represent knowledge (distortion). Both types of misrepresentation can occur very easily and cause malfunctions and result in the incorrect outputs. Malicious engineers know how to engineer bias and deviation by exploiting misrepresentation.

Principles and criteria to evaluate KR are shared with, and sometimes derived from, neighbouring disciplines, such as for example Formal Logic, Information Science and Ontology Engineering.

Adding KR quality and adequacy criteria to algorithmic auditing is therefore desirable and feasible. This section provides a set of criteria with corresponding justification and a checklist to facilitate this task for both developers and auditors.

5.1.2 Levels of Representation

Knowledge representations range from computer-oriented forms to conceptual ones nearer to those present in our internal world models. Five knowledge levels are identified in literature [20]:

Implementational: It includes data structures such as atoms, pointers, lists and other programming notations.

Logical: Symbolic logic is inside this level. Thus, symbolic logic propositions, predicates, variables, quantifiers and Boolean operations are included.

Epistemological: A level for defining concept types with subtypes, inheritance, and structuring relations.

Conceptual: The level of semantic relations, linguistic roles, objects and actions.

Linguistic: Deals with arbitrary concepts, words and expressions of natural languages

A new level emerges from practice to evaluate adequacy according to a Level of KR reality task-domain-system model, the functional system level (Image 2)

Image 2, Source 20

5.1.3. Adequacy

To be useful, KR needs to adhere to certain criteria and requirements, which at least in part are common to most types of information systems, knowledge bases and ontologies. Several types of **adequacy** criteria for of KR are known, such as:

Terminological adequacy the ability to form the appropriate kind of technical vocabulary and understand the dependencies among the terms;

Assertional adequacy involves the ability to form the kind of theory appropriate to the world knowledge of a system and understand the implications of the theory[21].

Other forms of quality metrics for KR include:

1. Representational Adequacy – the ability to represent all the different kinds of knowledge that might be needed in that domain.
2. Inferential Adequacy – the ability to manipulate the representational structures to derive new structures (corresponding to new knowledge) from existing structures.
3. Inferential Efficiency – the ability to incorporate additional information into the knowledge structure which can be used to focus the attention of the inference mechanisms in the most promising directions.
4. Acquisitional Efficiency– the ability to acquire new information easily. Ideally the agent should be able to control its own knowledge acquisition, but direct insertion of information by a

'knowledge engineer' would be acceptable.

Finding a single system that automates the optimisation these for all possible parameters is not always feasible, however researchers and developers are encouraged to develop and apply their own evaluation schemas for KR using as a reference and guidelines the criteria listed here. In the light of recent emphasis on AI safety, adequate KR should also address *FAT* (Fairness Accountability and Transparency) criteria and the identification of Risks and corresponding mitigation strategies as well as the identification of Bias, Sources of Bias and Debiasing techniques.

Quality evaluation for Algorithmic KR can take place across many dimensions:

Adequacy (Variety of Expressiveness, Modularity, Semantics, a Organization of Knowledge, conformance to a correct model of reality and other criteria);

Inference Methods (Reasoning Strategies, Data, Control and Search Strategies);

Inference Requirements (Computational Efficiency, Transparency of line of control, Completeness, and Consistency)

Ability to use a priori knowledge, and update it with newly-acquired knowledge.

Dealing with incomplete and imperfect knowledge.

Correctness Evaluation - the KR should include the ability to estimate its representational correctness [69,70,71,72]

6. Algorithmic Auditability Checklist based on KR

It is often argued that algorithmic auditing may not be entirely automated due to the inherent lack of replicability of probabilistic causal computation, using a combination of different KR techniques in triangulation facilitates the explicit representation and replication, even partial, of artificial neural network computation. A sample checklist is synthesized from good

practices in KR and offered here as a set of heuristic criteria to guide developers who may want to attempt creating an algorithm for algorithmic auditability, as well for auditors and developers of auditing methodologies:

Algorithmic Audit should identify and makes explicit:

Individuals/Components/Entities of the Algorithm

Axioms/Laws/Constraints/Limitations

Truth Values (consistency, persistence, conflicts)

Processes/Functions

Inputs/Outputs/Outcomes

Risks and Mitigation

Bias/De biasing options

Type Of Reasoning/Inference

Relevant Variables

Behaviours

Structure/Patterns

Levels Of Predictability Of The Behaviours (Probability, Randomness)

Influence Factors

Variables That May Influence Factors

Interactions

Type Of Notation/Encoding

Knowledge Level (Logical, Implementational, Epistemological, Conceptual, Linguistic, Task, Domain, System)

Overall Scientific/Computational Paradigm

Complete/Sufficiently Describing what it represents

Should Allow Manipulation Of The Representation For Testing/Evaluation Purposes

Human And Machine Readable

General FAT areas of concerns (Fairness Accountability Transparency)

6.1. Adding KR To KAF

The checklist, which evolves from general good practices in KR, can be used to inform system stakeholders, such as owners, managers and developers, and is the basis for the systemization of algorithmic audits awareness of possible areas of risk, where the algorithm can go wrong. It has been added to KAF in the form of a questionnaire ³ to be compiled by at least four roles

1. the system designer
2. the coders/programmers
3. the independent auditors
4. stakeholders and system users at large

7. Conclusions and Future Work

This paper brings together expertise and considerations from AI, KR, systems auditing to deliver criteria and a checklist that can be leveraged and integrated in any type of algorithmic auditing methodology, and that can also be used as a guide to inform and systematize algorithmic awareness auditing in different groups of stakeholders. Future work includes the evaluation of the impact of the checklist with case studies.

³ <https://sites.google.com/site/kaframework/>

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